

Studies on Benzenesulphonamidomethylbenzimidazoles. III. Condensation Products of N-Benzenesulphonyl L(+) Glutamic Acid with *O*-Phenylenediamine

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The condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid has been reported. The products obtained are (a) a simple salt, (b) a monobenzimidazole derivative and (c) a dibenzimidazole derivative. Amide of monobenzimidazole derivative, and its hydrochloride as well as hydrochlorides of the ethyl ester and dimethylamide of monobenzimidazole derivative and dihydrochloride of dibenzimidazole derivative have also been prepared. Their electronic spectra, ir spectra and also pK_a values have been recorded and a discussion has been made. Structure of monobenzimidazole derivative has been interpreted to be a zwitterion one, supported by pK_a and ir data.

IN order to synthesise benzimidazoles containing sulphonamido group, which are of considerable importance for their physiological activity¹⁻⁴ and also for acting as chelating agents⁵⁻⁷, N-benze-

sulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid⁸ has been condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine employing both the method of Philips⁹ and the method of fusion¹⁰. As a result a number of products, (a) a simple salt (I), (b) a

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monobenzimidazole derivative (II) and (c) a dibenzimidazole derivative (III), have been isolated. The

present communication deals with the characterization of the products (I), (II) and (III).

Amide (IV) of (II) and its hydrochloride as well as hydrochlorides of dimethylamide (V) and ethyl ester (VI) of (II) and hydrochloride of (III) have also been prepared.

Experimental

UV spectra were measured with a Hilger's UVISPEK spectrophotometer in ethanol and in water using matched 1 cm quartz cells. IR spectra were obtained with a BECKMAN IR-20 spectrophotometer in KBr disks. The pK_a values were determined using Cambridge Portable Type pH-Meter. Melting points recorded were uncorrected.

Method of Fusion: (A) An intimate mixture of mono-potassium salt of N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid¹¹ and *o*-phenylenediamine (0.04 moles each) was fused on glycerol bath at varying temperatures upto 210° for 10–15 min. In each case the reaction product was extracted with hot water, norited and filtered. Adding few drops of acetic acid ($pH \approx 3$) to the cooled filtrate, white crystals (I) separated. It was recrystallised from hot water. It is soluble in water, ethanol etc. m.p. 162° dec; uv spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 285 nm (log ϵ 3.30), 273 nm (3.31), 232 nm (4.44); ir spectrum (KBr) 3390, 2899, 1702, 1635, 1608, 1504, 1453, 1405, 1325, 1307, 1242, 1218, 1203, 1163, 1087, 990, 934, 751, 725, 691 cm^{-1} (Found : Eqv. wt., 197.0; C, 51.57; H, 5.53; N, 10.81; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{21}O_6N_3S$ (I) : Eqv. wt., 197.5; C, 51.64; H, 5.32; N, 10.63%).

The same compound was obtained simply by mixing concentrated solutions of N-benzenesulphonyl glutamic acid and *o*-phenylenediamine. Adding dilute H_2SO_4 to the concentrated ethanolic solution of $C_{17}H_{21}O_6N_3S$ (I) followed by cooling in ice bath, shining white crystals of *o*-phenylene diamine sulphate separated. Crystals were collected and washed with cold water, m.p. 220° dec; uv spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 282 nm (log ϵ 3.25); 238 nm (3.58); ir spectrum (KBr) 2845, 2564, 1603, 1511, 1322, 1262, 1175, 1122, 1065, 990, 892, 775, 763 cm^{-1} . (Found : Eqv. wt., 102.2; SO_4 , 46.96; Calcd. for $C_6H_{10}O_4N_2S$: Eqv. wt., 103.0; SO_4 , 46.60%).

(B) By fusing the same mixture as in (A) at temperatures 230°–235° until no evolution of gases (10–15 min), the reaction product was extracted with warm dilute HCl, norited and filtered. The pH of the filtrate was adjusted to ~ 4 with NaOH. A white compound separated. It was dissolved in dilute ammonia, norited and filtered. Now the pH of the filtrate was adjusted to ~ 4 with acetic acid. A white crystalline compound separated. Recrystallised from warm aqueous DMSO, white shining crystals were obtained. It is highly soluble in DMF, DMSO; slightly soluble in THF and dioxan; and practically insoluble in water, m.p. 236° dec; uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 281 nm (log ϵ 3.72), 275 nm (3.77), 236–235 nm (3.72); ir spectrum (KBr) 3175, 3077, 1648, 1613, 1600, 1527, 1478, 1457, 1389, 1325, 1233, 1168, 1093, 990, 925, 909, 892, 769, 740, 695 cm^{-1} .

(Found : Eqv. wt., 358; C, 57.03; H, 4.91; N, 11.73; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{17}O_4N_3S$ (II) : Eqv. wt., 359; C, 56.82; H, 4.73; N, 11.69%).

The hydrochloride of (II) was prepared by evaporating its HCl extract in vacuum over H_2SO_4 and KOH. It is hygroscopic, soluble in ethanol, water etc., uv spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 276 nm (log ϵ 3.80), 270 nm (3.82), 231–230 nm (3.78). (Found : Eqv. wt., 199.0; Cl, 9.30; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{17}O_4N_3S \cdot HCl$: Eqv. wt., 197.8; Cl, 8.98).

Sodium salt of (II) was prepared by extracting aqueous suspension of the compound (II) with dilute aqueous NaOH followed by evaporating the clear solution in vacuum over H_2SO_4 and KOH. It is also hygroscopic, soluble in water and ethanol, uv spectrum, $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 280 nm (log ϵ 3.74), 273 nm (3.77), 236–235 nm (3.76). (Found : Na, 5.53; Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_3Na \cdot 2H_2O$: Na, 5.52).

(C) An intimate mixture of 0.04 moles of N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid and 0.10 moles of *o*-phenylenediamine was fused for 10–20 min on glycerol bath at 160°–170°. The reaction product slowly became viscous and finally solidified. It was extracted with dilute HCl, norited and filtered. Then the pH of the filtrate was adjusted to about 9 with NH_3 . A white compound (III) separated. It was filtered. The filtrate was acidified by acetic acid to $pH \approx 4$. A white crystalline compound (II) separated. It was recrystallised from warm aqueous DMSO. Shining white crystals were obtained, m.p. 236° dec. The compound (III) separated at pH 9 was dissolved in dilute NaOH; norited, filtered and on addition of NH_4Cl solution to the filtrate white compound separated. It was again treated with NaOH and then with NH_4Cl as before. The compound was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . It is soluble in ethanol and insoluble in water. It decomposes on heating above 200°; uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 283 nm (log ϵ 4.15), 275 nm (4.10), 245 nm (4.00); ir spectrum (KBr) 3340, 3060, 1615, 1522, 1472, 1440, 1320, 1305, 1265, 1215, 1150, 1082, 1015, 960, 895, 830, 760, 735, 680 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 64.55; H, 5.18; N, 16.70; Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{21}O_2N_5S$ (III) : C, 64.03; H, 4.87; N, 16.24%).

A hygroscopic hydrochloride was obtained from ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution of $C_{23}H_{21}O_2N_5S$ (III) on evaporation. It was dried in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 and KOH. It is highly soluble in water, ethanol etc.; uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 278 nm (log ϵ 4.20), 272 nm (4.13), 226–225 nm (4.08). (Found : Eqv. wt., 253.6; Cl, 14.40; Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{21}O_2N_5S \cdot 2HCl$: Eqv. wt., 252.0; Cl, 14.09%).

Phillips method: An equimolecular mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine and monopotassium salt of N-benzenesulphonyl L(+) glutamic acid (0.04 moles each) in 45 ml 4N HCl was boiled under reflux for 4 hr. The pH of the cooled solution was adjusted to 9 first with NaOH and finally with NH_3 and filtered. The compound separated was dissolved in dilute NaOH solution, norited and filtered. On addition of NH_4Cl solution to the filtrate, the compound separated was found to be (III). The yield is

very low in comparison to that by fusion method. Although the yield could be increased by using double amount of *o*-phenylenediamine and increasing the time of reflux. Adjusting the pH of the filtrate (pH $\approx$ 9) to about 4 with acetic acid, a white crystalline compound separated. It was recrystallised from warm aqueous DMSO. White shining crystals (II) were obtained m.p. 236° dec. The yield is much better than that obtained by fusion method.

Amide of C₁₇H₁₇O₄N₃S (II) was prepared first by slow warming (II) on steam bath with slight excess of thionyl chloride in benzene for one hour, then by passing dry NH₃ to the cooled acid chloride derivative till saturation. The reaction product was then added to crushed ice. The residue obtained by filtration was dissolved in dilute NaOH, norited and filtered. On adding NH₄Cl solution to the filtrate, a white crystalline compound separated. It was recrystallised from warm aqueous DMSO, when white shining crystals were obtained, m.p. 110° dec; soluble in ethanol, DMSO, DMF etc. sparingly soluble in water, uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 276 nm (log ϵ 3.83), 272 nm (3.83), 227 nm (3.77); ir spectrum (KBr) 3636, 3431, 3226, 3077, 1695, 1639, 1613, 1457, 1439, 1396, 1325, 1296, 1282, 1248, 1161, 1097, 1006, 980, 926, 900, 800, 741, 697 cm⁻¹. (Found: C, 57.00; H, 5.10; N, 15.60; Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈O₃N₄S (IV): C, 56.98; H, 5.03; N, 15.64%).

Hydrochloride of C₁₇H₁₈O₃N₄S (IV) was obtained as shining white crystalline solid by dissolving the compound (IV) in minimum quantity of dilute HCl and then adding few drops of concentrated HCl to the clear solution. It is soluble in ethanol, DMSO, DMF etc., insoluble in CHCl₃. It was air dried; uv spectrum λ_{max}^{EtOH} 282 nm (log ϵ 3.90), 275 nm (3.89), 238 nm (3.90); ir spectrum (KBr) 3390, 3226, 2740, 2632, 2532, 1709, 1688, 1639, 1587, 1527, 1504, 1471, 1460, 1429, 1347, 1290, 1235, 1190; 1173, 1159, 1117, 1099, 1081, 1075, 1042, 1020, 990, 909, 855, 758, 730, 692 cm⁻¹. (Found: Eqv. wt., 392.0; Cl, 8.33; Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₈O₃N₄S HCl: Eqv. wt., 394.5; Cl, 9.00%).

Dimethylamide (V) of C₁₇H₁₇O₄N₃S (II) was prepared by passing dry dimethylamine to the acid chloride of (II) at a temperature 45°-60°. The reaction product was extracted with cold dilute NaOH solution, norited and filtered. On addition of NH₄Cl solution to the filtrate a semisolid mass separated. This was dissolved in hot ethanol, norited and filtered. From the filtrate white shining crystals separated which were air-dried. Hydrochloride of C₁₉H₂₂O₃N₄S (V) was obtained from its ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution as white crystalline solid by evaporating in a vacuum desiccator over H₂SO₄ and KOH. It is soluble in water, ethanol etc.; uv spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 281 nm (log ϵ 4.71), 274 nm (4.75), 238 nm (4.75); ir spectrum (KBr) 3260, 3070, 3010, 2960, 2910, 2840, 2800, 2710, 2630, 2600, 1630, 1558, 1500, 1470, 1450, 1440, 1395, 1380, 1325, 1305, 1280, 1250, 1212, 1152, 1125, 1070, 1015, 990, 955, 940, 895, 880, 845, 812, 745, 720, 680 cm⁻¹. (Found: Eqv. wt., 423.1; Cl, 8.45; Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₂O₃N₄S HCl. Eqv. wt., 422.5; Cl, 8.40%).

Ethyl ester (VI) of (II) was also prepared first by passing dry HCl gas through a suspension of (II) in ethanol till saturated, then refluxing on steam bath for 1 hr. Neutralizing the reaction product with NaHCO₃ after pouring in ice, a white compound separated. It was extracted with ether and on passing dry HCl gas to the dried ether solution a white hygroscopic compound separated. It was collected and dried under vacuum over H₂SO₄ and KOH. It is soluble in water, ethanol etc., uv spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{H_2O}$ 277 nm (log ϵ 4.93), 271 nm (4.91). (Found: Eqv. wt., 425.5; Cl, 8.31; Calcd. for C₁₉H₂₁O₄N₃S HCl: Eqv. wt., 423.5; Cl, 8.38%).

Determination of acid dissociation constants of various benzimidazolium derivatives: The experiments were carried out at 31° ± 1°. All pH-metric titrations were made at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) by adding requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. The results are stated in Table 1.

TABLE 1 pK_a VALUES OF THE BENZIMIDAZOLIUM IONS

Species	pK _{Benzimidazolium}	Species	pK _{Benzimidazolium}	pK _{COOH}
R ^b _m H ₂ ⁺	4.82 ⁶	(II H ⁺)	6.08	2.68
R ^t _m H ₂ ⁺	4.85 ⁶	(IV H ⁺)	5.74	—
R ^b _{ep} H ₂ ⁺	5.69 ⁶	(V H ⁺)	5.80	—
R ^t _{ep} H ₂ ⁺	5.70 ⁷	(VI H ⁺)	5.77	—

Results and Discussion

It is evident from analytical data (vide experimental section) that the compound (I) is a simple salt of *o*-phenylenediamine with N-benzenesulphonyl L(+)-glutamic acid (R^b_a H₃), which has been further confirmed by (a) treating the aqueous ethanolic solution of the salt with sulphuric acid when shining crystals of *o*-phenylenediamine sulphate C₆H₄(NH₂)₂.H₂SO₄ are obtained and (b) preparing it simply on mixing the aqueous solutions of R^b_a H₃ and *o*-phenylenediamine. But the compound (II) is monobenzimidazole derivative of R^b_a H₃, which may be represented by any one of the two alternative ways (IIa) or (IIb) as stated below:

Compound (II)
C₁₇H₁₇O₄N₃S

(IIa)

or

(IIb)

The amide of the compound (II) as well as its hydrochloride and also hydrochlorides of dimethylamide and ethyl ester of (II) have been prepared and their pK_a values (Table 1) have been determined potentiometrically¹². Comparing the pK_{COOH} values of (II) with these for the starting material $R_m^bH_2$ ($pK_2 = 2.99$; $pK_1 = 4.53$)¹³; N-benzenesulphonyl-

glycine ($pK_{COOH} = 3.21$)¹⁴; N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl-glycine ($pK_{COOH} = 3.26$)¹⁴; N-benzenesulphonyl- β -alanine ($pK_{COOH} = 4.18$)¹⁴; N-*p*-toluenesulphonyl- β -alanine ($pK_{COOH} = 4.20$)¹⁴ and $pK_{Benzimidazolium\ ion}$ of (II) with that for $R_m^bH_2^+$; $R_m^tH_2^+$; $R_{e\beta}^bH_2^+$; $R_{e\beta}^tH_2^+$ (Table 1), it is obvious that the compound (II) is actually (IIa).

(R_{eβ}^tH₂⁺)

TABLE 2—SOME IR BANDS OF INTEREST ALONG WITH THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS

Compounds and ir Bands in Cm⁻¹

I	II	III	IV	IV H ⁺ Cl ⁻	V H ⁺ Cl ⁻	Probable assignments		
3390 r	3175 m	3340 s	3636 w	3390 m	3260 s	O-H	C-H,	N-H
2899 m	3077 m	3060 s	3431 m	3226 s	3070 s			
..	..	..	3226 m	..	2910 s	stretches		
1702 s	..	..	3077 m	..	2840 s	due to COOH		
..	..	..	1695 s	1709 s	..	due to CONH ₂		
..	1648 m	1615 m	1639 w	(1688 s)	1630 s	C = N stretches		
1635 s	1613 s	..	..	1639 m	..	COO antisymmetrical stretches		
1608 s	..	..	..	..	..	due to NH ₃ ⁺		
1504 s	1600 s	1522 m	1613 s	1587 m	1558 m	aromatic C = C skeletal		
1453 s	1527 m	1472 m	1457 m	1504 m	1500 m			
..	1478 m	1440 s	1439 m	1471 m	1470 m	in-plane vibrations		
..	1457 m	..	..	1460 m	1450 s			
1405 s	1389 s	..	..	..	..	COO symmetrical stretches		
1325 m	1325 s	1320 s	1325 m	1347 s	1325 s	SO ₂ -N band II		
1242 s	..	..	1248 w	1235 m	..	due to COOH		
..	..	..	1296 m	1290 m	..	due to CONH ₂		
1307 s	1233 m	1305 s	1296 m	1190 m	1305 s	in-plane C-H deformation		
1218 m	1093 m	1265 s	1282 m	1173 s	1280 m			
1203 s	..	1215 w	1097 s	1099 s	1212 m	ring breathing modes		
1087 s	..	1082 s	..	1159 s	1070 s			
1163 s	1168 s	1150 s	1161 s	1159 s	1152 s	SO ₂ -N band I		
990 m	990 m	1015 w	1006 w	1020 w	1015 w	benzenoid ring		
934 w	925 w	960 w	980 w	990 m	990 w			
..	..	..	926 w	..	940 m	breathing modes		
..	909 w	895 w	990 w	909 m	895 w	heterocyclic ring		
..	892 w	830 w	800 w	855 m	845 m			
..	769 w	760 m	..	758 s	812 s	breathing modes		
751 s	740 s	735 s	741 s	730 s	745 s	out-of-plane		
725 m	695 m	680 m	697 m	692 m	720 s			
691 m	..	..	..	..	680 m	C-H deformation		

However the dibenzimidazole derivative (III) is ultimately formed by condensing (II) with excess of *o*-phenylenediamine by Phillips method and also by fusing $R_6^6H_3$ with *o*-phenylenediamine.

Higher $pK_{Benzimidazolium\ ion}$ value (6.08) for (II) than that for amide, dimethylamide, ethyl ester derivatives and lower pK_{COOH} (2.68) than that for $R_6^6H_3$, indicate the existence of zwitterion structure¹⁵ which is also supported by ir data—disappearance of the band at 1709 cm^{-1} of (I) due to COOH groups. The compound (II) may therefore be represented as stated below :

Electronic absorption spectra of the compounds and their salts in ethanolic solution and also some of them in aqueous solution show a number of peaks in the uv region. The uv spectrum of benzimidazole resembles that of a substituted benzene¹⁶. The uv peaks recorded here are closely comparable to those found in a number of substituted benzimidazoles¹⁷. Some ir band of interest along with their probable assignments¹⁷⁻²⁰ are shown in Table 2. These data support the structural arrangements of the compounds as stated herein.

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